

Greener Journal of Plant Breeding and Crop Science

ISSN: 2354-2292

Morphological Characterization of Two Species of Piper, *Piper umbellatum* and *Piper capense* in Tepi, Ethiopia

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the intra and inter-specific relationships between the two species, using five accessions of *Piper umbellatum* and eight of *Piper capense*. 13 quantitative characters (seven vegetative and six reproductive) and 16 qualitative characters were pooled for the analysis.

These two species were found to differ in stem colour, hairiness (*pubescence*) and branching habit. Leaf blades were found broadly ovate in *p. capense* but sub orbicular-ovate in *p. umbellatum*, leaf base cordate in *p. capense* but deeply cordate in *p. umbellatum*, Leaf vein 7-9 veined from base, hairy at least on veins below in *p. capense* but 9-11 veined from base with 2 additional major veins arising just above base in *p. umbellatum*,. Stipules 1.5-2cmL in *p. capense* but 2-2.5cmL in *p. umbellatum*, Spike solitary in *p. capense* but inflorescence an apparently auxiliary pedunculate umbel of up to 5 spikes in *p. umbellatum*,. Flowering period was longer in *p. capense* (>15 days) than in *p. umbellatum* (maximum of 9 days). Taller plant were recorded for *p. capense* 2.7m(L), shorter plant height were recorded for *p. umbellatum*, 1m(L), Greater intra-specific variation was observed in *p. capense* (five clusters) than in *p. umbellatum*, (three clusters) the species showed closer inter-specific relationship at higher Euclidean distance.

Keywords: clustering, morphology, *piper capense*, *piper umbellatum*, south western Ethiopia, Variability.

INTRODUCTION

Piper capense and *piper umbellatum* known as Timize (Amaharic) in Ethiopia, they are in the family *peperaceae* and the genus *piper*. It is grown under the lower strata of natural forest of Kefa, Sheka and Bench Maji zone often as a spice and medicinal plant and it is collected widely for its mature fruit. This spice has not yet been under cultivated; the people in the region collect it from the lower strata of dense forests for market sell only (Girma et.al, 2008).

It is also popular in Africa, mostly in Islamic regions of north and east Africa, It can be found in the complex spice mixtures of Morocco and Ethiopia (to spice mutton dishes). It is also found in traditional meat stews (WOT) together with black pepper, nutmeg, cloves and turmeric in Ethiopia (Jiwari & Agarwal, 2004).

However, like most tropical crops, very little attention has been devoted to this versatile crop. Its genetic diversity is clearly shown by the wide range of morphological characteristics displayed by the taxon in different eco-geographical, edaphic, and environmental condition. This may well point to the considerable genetic resources inherent in the genus in particular the taxon piper, which is indigenous to the region and which is widely used by the people (Girma & Degafe, 1997).

The current interest in Timize has arisen because of a perceived ambiguity in the status of the genus piper section, particularly known as Ethiopian Timize which is quite diverse and shows a wide range of morph-agronomic character. These groups of related plants are not well known and share a wide range of trait with cultivated Indian *Piper longum*. Consequently, there is confusion about their classification. *Piper capense* and *Piper umbellatum* were collected and are indigenous to the country (Anonymous, 1995). Edwards et.al, (2000), distinguished three indigenous, two is wild and one is cultivated. According to Jiwari (2004), long pepper which tastes pungent and sweet at the same time, probably came to Europe much before the dominant black pepper plant. Later, Pruthi (2001) says that long pepper is the dried fruit of *Piper longum*, which is a slender, aromatic climber with perennial woody roots. Recently, Sujatha and Nybe (2007) reported that *Piper longum* L., commonly called Pippali or Tippali, is an herb of immense medicinal use. Further more Girma et.al (2008), said that long pepper is a perennial shrub and one of the indigenous spices given consideration in the research. The complexity of the genus often leads to misidentification

and uncertainty among taxonomists and hinders breeding section efforts. The present practice is to isolate a large and diverse as the North West Ethiopian Timith which, share a range of morpho-agaronomic (vegetative and reproductive) characters, emphasizing the complexity of the genus. The present study seeks to clarify this complexity (inter-and intra-specific relationships) among the accession.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Thirteen accessions of the genus piper were sourced for the present study. The whole accessions were procured from Tepi National Spices Research Centre. The accessions were grown 3*3m plot size in RCBD with three replications. The accession were planted March 2000 and harvested from May 2003 to 2005, quantitative and qualitative data was compared. Fifteen qualitative characters (nine vegetative and six reproductive) and thirteen quantitative characters (7 vegetative and 6, reproductive) were recorded and data were pooled for analysis. Leaf characteristic of the old and young leaves from the apex were recorded in order to obtain full expression of characters. Floral characters were recorded on five flowers from each accession. Fruit characters were recorded from five mature fruit. A hierarchical cluster analysis, coefficient of variation on the un-weighted pair group method, was carried out using SAS software package. Squared Euclidean distance was used as a measure of distance for cluster formation after standardization of quantitative data

Table: 1. Pedigree of the collected accessions

S/.no	Species	Accession Code.	Origin (wereda)	Latitude	lNgitude
1	<i>P.umbellatum</i>	Lp.040	Yeki	07 ⁰ 10.74N	035 ⁰ 29.59E
2	<i>P.umbellatum</i>	Lp.051	Godere	07 ⁰ 17.62N	035 ⁰ 16.17E
3	<i>P.umbellatum</i>	Lp.077	Sheko	07 ⁰ 03.60N	035 ⁰ 26.60E
4	<i>P.umbellatum</i>	Lp.073	Sheko	07 ⁰ 07.67N	035 ⁰ 26.04E
5	<i>P.umbellatum</i>	Lp.0101	Maji	07 ⁰ 32.63N	036 ⁰ 28.72E
6	<i>p.capense</i>	Lp.098	Decha	07 ⁰ 13.86N	036 ⁰ 13.44E
7	<i>p.capense</i>	Lp.017	Gimbo	07 ⁰ 19.53N	036 ⁰ 14.65E
8	<i>p.capense</i>	Lp.019	Gimbo	07 ⁰ 19.71N	036 ⁰ 13.47E
9	<i>p.capense</i>	Lp.076	Sheko	07 ⁰ 03.60N	035 ⁰ 26.60E
10	<i>p.capense</i>	Lp.025	Gimbo	07 ⁰ 30.17N	036 ⁰ 03.28E
11	<i>p.capense</i>	Lp.092	Decha	07 ⁰ 09.90N	036 ⁰ 13.06E
12	<i>p.capense</i>	Lp.094	Decha	07 ⁰ 07.62N	036 ⁰ 11.15E
13	<i>p.capense</i>	Lp.028	Gimbo	07 ⁰ 16.72N	036 ⁰ 12.90E

Sources: Tepi National Spies Research Centre “mid and low land Ethiopia spices collection” sheet (unpublished).

Figure.1. Zones where the accessions collected

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Qualitative Characters

Amongst the accession studied, both the accession was shrubby herb, and some what woody at the base, the growth pattern was generally indeterminate and Steam type was weak, flexible and procumbent for all accession of *p. capense* and *p. umbellatum*. Deep green coloration of the steam was recorded in *p. capense* and light green for *p. umbellatum*. Hairiness (pubescence) was slightly pronounced in all *p. umbellatum* accession conspicuous in *p. capense*. All accession of *p. umbellatum* showed moderate orthotropic branching while *p. capense* showed strongly branched. Steam internodes were long in *p. capense*, short in *p. umbellatum*, it ranged from 20cm (lp17-lp052) generally internodes length decrease when we go up ward in *p. capense* but the reverse in *p. umbellatum*, fruit shape was oblong for both species. The position of the fruit in relation to the steam was parallel for *p. capense* but slightly horizontal for *p. umbellatum*, fruit surface were slightly rough in *p. umbellatum* but rough in *p. capense*. Leaf blade broadly ovate in *p. capense* but sub orbicular-ovate in *p. umbellatum*, leaf base cordet in *p. capense* but deeply cordet in *p. umbellatum*. Leaf tip acuminate in both species. Leaf vain 7-9 veined from base, hairy at least on veins below in *p. capense* but 9-11 veined from base with 2 additional major veins arising just above base in *p. umbellatum*, Veins densely pubrulent below in *p. umbellatum*. Stipule 1.5-2cmL in *p. capense* but 2-2.5cmL in *p. umbellatum* spike solitary in *p. capense* but inflorescence an apparently auxiliary pedunculate umbel of up to 5 spikes in *p. umbellatum*.

Figure 2. (A), *p. umbellatum* (B), *p. capense*

Quantitative characteristics

The standard deviation (an index of the disparity between 11 characters), the range and coefficient of variation showed a high degree of variability among the thirteen accessions analyzed. The accession start flowering at the beginning of March and end at the mid of November, but they flower, fruiting simultaneously. Flowering period was longer in *p. capense* (>15 days) than in *P. umbellatum* (maximum of 9 days). Range of flowering day varies within the accession and between the accession, it ranges 12 (lp098-lp40). *P. capense* produce more fruit (343) than *P. umbellatum*, (78). Number of fruit produced per plant ranged from 343 in accession lp019 (*p. capense*) to 78 in accession lp040 (*p. capense*), there is a wide variation in fruit number within the species and between species too. Generally, lower and highest number of fruit recorded for *p. capense* accession. The highest number of fruit produced by *p. capense* accession may be connected with the longer flowering period (and thus fruiting) period, although it may be the effect of other factor such as genetic composition.

There was marked difference between the species in reproductive trait analyzed. The range of days between fruit setting to fruit maturity (fruiting period) was higher for most *p. capense* accession than for *p. umbellatum* accession, it ranges 66(lp076-lp052). Pedicle length, were greater in *p. capense* accession than *p. umbellatum* accession, it ranges 2.65cm (lp025-lp40). Toler Fruit length was recorded for *p. umbellatum* accession than *p. capense* accession it ranges 7.25cm (lp030-lp092). Internode length was higher in *p. capense* accession than in *p. umbellatum* accession it, ranges 20cm (lp017-lp052). Maximum and minimum thousand fruit weights were recorded for *p. capense* accession than *p. umbellatum* accession 1783.14 gram (lp019) and 9 4 8 gram (lp094) .

Similarly, taller plant were recorded for *p. capense*; 2.7m, shorter plant height were recorded for *p. umbellatum* accession; 1m. Maximum and minimum number of suckers was recorded for *p. umbellatum* accession it ranges 39 (lp101-lp40). There is highest variability in number of sucker within specious and highest number of sucker does not refer to highest yields because it uses the sucker as a means of regeneration and reproduction. Number of fruit per pedicle ranges 5 (in all *p. umbellatum* accession) and 1 (in all *p. capense* accession) However, the strong branching habit recorded for *p. capense* points to a high yield potential, as branches are production site and hence the higher their number, the greater the potential yield.

Table: 2. Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), Range and Co-efficient of Variation (CV) for the 13 quantitative characteristics

S/N	Character	Mean	SD	Range	CV
1	Fruiting period	81	21.27	66(lp076-lp052)	3.94
2	Flowering period (day)	8.26	3.36	12(lp098-lp40)	10.56
3	Plant height(cm)	1.72	0.34	1.7(lp025-lp052)	12.89
4	Fruit length(cm)	3.79	2.1	7.25(lp030-lp092)	19.5
5	Pedicle length(cm)	1.78	0.83	2.65(lp025-lp40)	41.48
6	Single fruit Weight (gram)	1.6358	0.44	1.301(lp101-lp094)	0.18
7	Total No. of fruit/plant	71.67	119.28	340(lp019-lp094)	144.73
8	1000 fresh fruit Weight(gram)	1401.326	264.19	835.1(lp019-lp094)	644.27
9	No. of suckers/stand	25.5	16.695	39(lp101-lp40)	60.64
10	No. of fruit per pedicle	2.54	1.97	4(lp40,051,098,101,073-lp092,94,28,)	0.1
11	Internodes length (cm)	17.57	4.73	20(lp017-lp052)	15.0
12	Leaf length (cm)	14.97	4.23	15(Lp051-Lp028)	7.4
13	Leaf width (cm)	16.76	8.39	27.5(Lp051-Lp028)	8.77

Cluster analysis

The degree of intra-specific variation differs for the two groups of accession. They form two clearly separated clusters. *P. capense* form five sub cluster, cluster: lp092 & lp025, lp019&lp017, lp094&lp098 form a cluster; and accession lp076 and lp028 each forms a single cluster (figure 1 and table 3). The grouping of most the *P. capense* accession in one cluster indicates a high degree of morphological similarity within the species. Nevertheless, the separation of the single cluster (lp076 and lp028) shows a considerable degree of morphological variation within the species. Conversely, the *p. umbellatum* accession form three cluster: lp077 form a single cluster, lp040, lp051 form a cluster and lp101, and lp073 form a cluster. The accession lp101 and lp073 separated from *p. umbellatum* accession and form cluster to that of *P. capense*, this shows as high degree of inter specific similarity within the species and lp077 form a distinct single cluster and it is high dissimilarity to all accession in the study.

At a higher Euclidian distance, three distinct clusters are formed. This is indicative of inter-specific morphological dissimilarity between the two groups of accessions.

Figure.3. HIERARCHICAL CLUSTERING, Method = Ward

Table: 3 CLUSTERING HISTORY

Number of Clusters	Distance	Leader	Joiner
12	0.662595075	lp40	lp051
11	0.821184952	lp094	lp098
10	0.984633018	lp092	lp025
9	1.241210568	lp019	lp17
8	1.252230885	lp094	lp028
7	1.397205007	lp092	lp076
6	1.857760681	lp101	lp073
5	2.151200037	lp40	lp077
4	2.585643825	lp092	lp019
3	4.125635059	lp092	lp094
2	5.539376393	lp092	lp101
1	6.195660365	lp40	lp092

CONCLUSION

The degree of morphological variation recorded among the accession indicates wide difference that may require further evidence, probably molecular, to clarify. These variations represent a vast genetic pool for breeding and improvement of the species as a whole.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I'm very grateful to Tepi agricultural research centre for providing all the accession and for all my friends for their help through out the development of this paper.

REFERENCES

- Girma H and Degaie T., 1997. Review of the past and recent research advances on mid and low altitude area spices research, IEAR, Addis Ababa.
- Girma H., Digafe T., Edossa E., Belay Y. and Weyessa, G. 2008. Spices research achievement revised edition, EIAR, Addis ababa, Ethiopia.
- Pruthi J.S. 2001. Minor spice and condiments crop management and post harvest technology, Indian council of agricultural research, New Delhi, India. pp575
- Jiwari R.S. and Ararwal A., 2004. Production technology of spices, international Book distributing Co. India. pp 356.
- Sue Edwards, Mesfin Tadesse, Sebsebe Demissew and Inga Hedberg, ed. 2000. Flora of Ethiopia and Eritrea, volume 2, part 1, Magnoliaceae to Flacourtiaceae, Uppsala, Sweden, and Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Sujatha V.S and Nybe E.V., 2007. A new sex form in pippali (*piper longum* L.), department of plantation crops and spices, college of horticulture, Plant genetic resources Newsletter No.149, 2007, Vellankkara, Thrissure, Kerala, India.